

The Effect of Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy on the Sustainability of Fishermen's Business in Bone Bolango

Radia Hafid¹, Melizubaida Mahmud², Ahmad Husain³, Raymondo Guga⁴

^{1,2}Lecturer at Economic Education Study Program, Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, Gorontalo, Indonesia

^{3,4}Student at Economic Education Study Program, Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, Gorontalo, Indonesia

Abstract:- Business continuity is a stability of business conditions which includes addition and continuation to protect business continuity and business expansion for the long term. This long-term value can be increased consistently and stable in business performance that can implement, among other things, the values that exist from within the entrepreneur himself. Based on this, this study aims to examine the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurial self-efficacy on the sustainability of fish catch business in Bonebolango Regency. This research is a non-experimental explanatory research with multiple linear regression analysis. The population in this study were 50 fish catch businesses of fishing communities in Bonebolango Regency, all of which were sampled. The results of the study prove that the characteristics of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial self-efficacy have an effect on business sustainability both partially and simultaneously.

Keywords:- Business Sustainability; Characteristics of Entrepreneurship; Self-Efficacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional fishing communities are people who work as fishermen who use various levels of existing fisheries technology. The livelihoods of fishing communities are mostly in the fishery sector and the utilization of marine resources (marine-based resources), namely as fishermen and fish farmers with pond and marine resources.

When viewed from the type of business, there are two types, namely family businesses and non-family businesses. Bonebolango Regency has a family business, especially the marine sector, which plays an important role in the regional economy, but in fact there are several marine-based businesses that have managed to last a long time and not a few marine-based family businesses in Kabila Bone District have failed.

For business to be better, basically an entrepreneur must have knowledge about entrepreneurship. In addition, entrepreneurs must have characteristics that must be owned by an entrepreneur. Because it is one of the drivers of entrepreneurs to achieve success in starting. This is also emphasized by Noor (2007:397) who argues that "business success is essentially the success of achieving goals, a

business is said to be successful if it makes a profit because profit is the goal of someone doing business".

The area in Bonebolango Regency with residents whose people are fishermen is an area in Kabila Bone District. The sub-district consists of 9 villages namely; Huangobotu, Molotabu, Oluhuta, Botubarani, Biluango, Modelomo, Botutonuo, Olele and Bintalahe are very long coastal marine areas (BPS Bonebolango, 2020).

Furthermore, in order to optimize the potential for business sustainability in Bonebolango Regency, it will not work if it is not balanced with self-efficacy for fishermen in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy owned by fishermen will provide maximum results if the fishermen believe in themselves that they are capable of entrepreneurship. However, in fact, not all fishermen have high entrepreneurial self-efficacy, it is shown that most fishermen feel less confident that they can succeed in entrepreneurship and are actually afraid of the risk of failure that cannot be overcome later.

Meanwhile, entrepreneurial self-efficacy can be a measure of a person's intentions towards something that is believed. Opening a business requires belief in one's own abilities that the business will succeed. Self-confidence is what will grow one's entrepreneurial motivation and self-efficacy. If someone is not confident in their abilities, it is unlikely that that person will have entrepreneurial motivation and self-efficacy. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy begins before someone decides to become an entrepreneur, then commits to the decisions that have been made, which in turn can bridge the gap in the next act.

This study seeks to examine the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurial self-efficacy on business sustainability (study on the fish catch business of fishing communities in Kabila Bone District, Bonebolango Regency).

Previously, there had been many similar studies conducted related to efforts to empower fishing communities, but all of them stopped after the community empowerment efforts had been completed, in other words no follow-up was carried out after the theoretical and practical contributions from the research were carried out. Departing from this, it is hoped that this research will further follow up on efforts to

empower fishing communities by looking at and testing the factors of other variables that are used as goals in empowering fishing communities.

This research is more devoted to fishing communities producing fish catches, namely by looking at and testing how the sustainability of the fishing community's fish catches is influenced by entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Business sustainability is condition of a business, in which there are ways to maintain, develop and protect resources and meet the needs that exist in a business (industry), the methods used are sourced from one's own experience, other people, and based on economic conditions or conditions that are happening in the business world so that business sustainability is a form of consistency of business conditions, where sustainability is a process of ongoing business both including growth, development, strategies to maintain business continuity and business development where all of this leads to the sustainability and existence (resilience) of the business according to Handayani, (in, widayanti et al, 2017. Business sustainability is a condition when a business has sufficient funds to run and develop its business, (Wibowo, 2012).

Entrepreneurial characteristics have an important role in shaping one's mental attitude, innovation power, creativity, courage, perseverance, hard work spirit, fighting power that synergizes with knowledge, skills and vigilance to determine business success (Soearsono, in Djoko Santoso, 2020).

Entrepreneurs who have entrepreneurial characteristics can face the problems and obstacles they face.

People who believe in themselves are capable of entrepreneurship, will be more likely to act and will be more likely to make themselves successful than people who do not have confidence in entrepreneurship. Self-efficacy is belief in one's own ability to deal with and solve problems effectively, self-efficacy also means believing oneself to be able to succeed and succeed (Farid Yapon, 2013).

III. METHOD

This research is an associative research type with a quantitative approach that aims to examine the influence between variables, namely the influence of entrepreneurial characteristics (X1) and entrepreneurial self-efficacy (X2) on business sustainability (Y). The research instrument used is a questionnaire generated from the adoption of previous research on business sustainability (noor 2007)), entrepreneurial characteristics (Suryana, 2018), entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Endi Sarwoko, 2011). The population in this study were all fishing fishermen who had a fish catch business in Kabila Bone District, Bonebolango Regency, totaling 50 fishermen and all of them were used as samples in this study.

The data analysis technique used in this research is multiple linear regression analysis technique using SPSS version 21 software application. Hypothesis testing uses t test to determine partial effect and F test to determine effect simultaneously. Research on the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics, motivation and self-efficacy on business sustainability can be illustrated in the following figure:

Fig 1:- Research Paradigm Model

Information:

X1: Characteristics of Entrepreneurs

X2: Motivation and Self Efficacy

Y : Business sustainability

--- : Partial influence

— : Simultaneous influence

β : Regression coefficient of each independent variable

Based on the research paradigm model supported by theoretical studies, the hypothesis (H) proposed in this study is:

H1: Characteristics of entrepreneurship partially have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability

H2: Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy partially has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability

H3: Entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the researcher presents the results of the research and discussion (discussion). The results section will discuss the results of the validity and reliability tests, hypothesis testing (t test and F test), the coefficient of determination and multiple linear regression models, and the discussion section will explain more specifically about the results of the findings in this study.

In the discussion section, the researcher will explore the relationship between the findings of this study and previous studies. The instrument used in this study has been tested for validity and reliability so that it can be relied upon in data collection. The results of the instrument item validity test for the entrepreneurial character variable (X1) are in the following table:

Items	r _{count}	r _{table 5%} df = (N-2)	Sig.	Criteria
1	0.911	0,278	0.000	Valid
2	0.868		0.000	Valid
3	0.917		0.000	Valid
4	0.820		0.000	Valid
5	0.950		0.000	Valid
6	0.805		0.000	Valid
7	0.938		0.000	Valid
8	0.893		0.000	Valid
9	0.802		0.000	Valid
10	0.935		0.000	Valid
11	0.815		0.000	Valid
12	0.774		0.000	Valid

Table 1:- The results of the validity test of the entrepreneurial character variable instrument
Source: Data Processed (2022)

Furthermore, the results of the validity test of the self-efficacy self-efficacy instrument (X2) were obtained as follows:

Items	r _{count}	r _{table 5%} df = (N-2)	Sig.	Criteria
1	0.668	0,278	0.000	Valid
2	0.655		0.000	Valid
3	0.759		0.000	Valid
4	0.818		0.000	Valid
5	0.559		0.000	Valid
6	0.585		0.000	Valid
7	0.825		0.000	Valid
8	0.767		0.000	Valid
9	0.470		0.001	Valid
10	0.647		0.000	Valid
11	0.570		0.000	Valid
12	0.724		0.000	Valid

Table 2:- The results of the instrument validity test of the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable
Source: Data Processed (2022)

Furthermore, the results of the validity test of the business sustainability instrument items (Y) are obtained as follows:

Items	r _{count}	r _{table 5%} df = (N-2)	Sig.	Criteria
1	0.442	0,278	0.001	Valid
2	0.457		0.001	Valid
3	0.725		0.000	Valid
4	0.466		0.001	Valid
5	0.478		0.000	Valid
6	0.633		0.000	Valid
7	0.636		0.000	Valid
8	0.751		0.000	Valid
9	0.633		0.000	Valid
10	0.455		0.001	Valid
11	0.306		0.031	Valid
12	0.454		0.001	Valid
13	0.665		0.000	Valid
14	0.694		0.000	Valid
15	0.707		0.000	Valid
16	0.689		0.000	Valid
17	0.589		0.000	Valid
18	0.792		0.000	Valid
19	0.733		0.000	Valid
20	0.727		0.000	Valid
21	0.657		0.000	Valid

Table 3:- The results of the instrument validity test for business sustainability variables
Source: Data Processed (2022)

Based on the instrument validity test of all variables, namely the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1), the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) and the business sustainability variable (Y), the results show that all instrument items are categorized as valid and suitable to be used as test instruments. The next stage is the instrument reliability test. Reliability test was conducted to measure the level of instrument reliability. The instrument is said to have a high reliability value if the tests carried out have consistent results in measuring what is being measured. Instrument reliability was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

The criteria used in the reliability test is if the result of r count has a value equal to or greater than the value of r table (r count ≥ r table) then the instrument is declared reliable. While the items are considered unreliable if the result of r count has a value smaller than the value of r table (r count < r table). To determine the reliability of the research instrument used, the researcher used the IBM SPSS statistics program version 21.0. The test results show that all items for the variables of entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and business sustainability are in the reliable category.

No	Variable	Cronbach Alpha	R _{table}	Criteria
1.	Characteristics of Entrepreneurs (X1)	0.971	0,600	Reliable
2.	Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (X2)	0.533	0,600	Reliable
3.	Business sustainability(Y)	0.900	0,600	Reliable

Table 4:- Instrument reliability test results
Source: Data Processed (2022)

Next is the result of testing the hypothesis (t test) partially used to partially test the effect of each independent variable (X1 and X2) on the dependent variable (Y). If the significance number (Sig.) < Probability 0.5 or Tcount > T table, this means that the independent variables (entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy) partially have a significant effect on the dependent variable (business sustainability). If the significance number

(Sig.) > Probability 0.5 or Tcount < Ttable, this means that the independent variables (entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy) partially have no significant effect on the dependent variable (business sustainability). The probability value used is = 0.05 and the magnitude of T_{table} is searched based on the formula df = n-k, where n = the number of respondents (sample) while k = the number of variables (free + bound). So df = 50 – 3 = 47, ttable is 2,011.

Model	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3,049	,004
Characteristics Entrepreneurs	2,190	,034
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	4,717	,000

Table 5:- Results of t-test (partial)
Source: Data Processed (2022)

From the results of the table above, it can be seen that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) has a significance value (Sig.) of $0.034 < 0.05$, while the tcount value is $2.190 > 2.011$ so it can be concluded that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable has a partial effect on business sustainability. The entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) has a significance value (Sig.) of $0.000 < 0.05$, while the t-value is $4.717 > 2.011$, so it can be concluded that the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable has a partial effect on business sustainability.

Next is the result of simultaneous hypothesis testing (F test). Simultaneous test aims to determine whether the

independent variables (entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy) have a joint influence on the dependent variable (business sustainability). This test uses the criteria if the p-value $<$ from the specified level of significance, the independent variables simultaneously affect the dependent variable or can see the F value. If the $F_{count} > F_{table}$, the independent variables simultaneously affect the dependent variable. F_{table} can be calculated by means of $df_1 = k-1$ and $df_2 = n-k$, where k is the number of dependent and independent variables. Then $df_1 = 3-1 = 2$ and $df_2 = 50-3 = 47$, so F_{table} is 2.80.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1256,095	2	628,047	30,928	,000^b
Residual	954,405	47	20,306		
Total	2210,500	49			

Table 6:- F test results (simultaneous)
Source: Data Processed (2022)

From the table above, it can be seen that the value of $F_{count} = 30.928$ and $F_{table} = 2.80$, so $F_{count} > F_{table}$, meaning that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) and the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) have the same effect on the sustainability variable (Y). The significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ means that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) and the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) have the same significant effect on the sustainability variable of fishing business in Kabila Bone District, Bonebolango District.

Next is testing the coefficient of determination which aims to measure the model's ability to explain the dependent variable. If R^2 is getting bigger (closer to one), it can be said that the influence of the independent variable is equal to the dependent variable. This means that the model used is getting stronger to explain the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. While R^2 (close to zero) it can be interpreted that the influence of the independent variables (X1 and X2) on the dependent variable (Y) is getting smaller, meaning that the model used is not strong enough to explain the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,754^a	,568	,550	4,50627

Table 7:- The results of the coefficient of determination
Source: Data Processed (2022)

From the results of the data analysis in the table above, the value of $R = 0.754$ and $R \text{ Square} = 0.568$. This means that the regression model obtained is able to explain that the variables of entrepreneurial characteristics (X1) and

entrepreneurial self-efficacy (X2) can affect the sustainability of fishing business in Kabila Bone District, Bonebolango Regency by 56.8%. Next, the results of the multiple linear regression model testing are shown in the table below:

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	23,120	7,584		3,049	,004
1 Characteristics Entrepreneurs	,271	,124	,263	2,190	,034
Entrepreneurial self-efficacy	,937	,199	,566	4,717	,000

Table 8:- Multiple linear regression model test

Source: Data Processed (2022)

Based on the data in the table above, the following regression equation is obtained:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

So from the above model, the output results can be entered as follows:

$$Y = 23,120 + 0,271X_1 + 0,937X_2 + e$$

The constant value is 23.120, this means that if it is assumed that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) and the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) are equal to zero, the business continuity will remain or not change by one unit 23,120. assuming other variables are fixed or constant.

The regression coefficient value of the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) is 0.271, this means that the entrepreneurial characteristic variable (X1) has a positive effect on business sustainability or in other words, every time there is an increase in the entrepreneurial characteristic variable by one unit, the business sustainability will increase by 0.271 with the assumption of other variables. is constant or constant.

The regression coefficient value of the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) is 0.937, this means that the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable (X2) has a positive effect on business sustainability or in other words, every time there is an increase in the entrepreneurial self-efficacy variable by one unit, business sustainability will increase by 0.937 with the assumption other variables are fixed or constant.

➤ **H1: Characteristics of entrepreneurship partially have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability**

The test results on hypothesis 1 (H1) state that the entrepreneurial characteristics partially have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. The findings of this study are in line with research conducted by (Sari, 2016) which states that entrepreneurial characteristics greatly determine business success. Business performance is strongly supported by the entrepreneurial characteristics that exist in an entrepreneur (Setyawati, 2013). Entrepreneurial characteristics are qualities or traits that remain continuous and eternal that can be used as characteristics to identify a person, an object, an event, integration or synthesis of individual traits in the form of a person or entity and a person's personality, considered from an ethical and moral point of

view. Entrepreneurial characteristics are the key to maximizing efficiency from the use of factors for developing economic competitiveness, enabling a business to have a more positive mindset, building market sensitivity and creating creative thinking (Sari, 2016).

Furthermore, this research is supported by research conducted by Ardiansyah (2017) which states that the success of an entrepreneur is to have a creative and innovative character. In addition, Setyawati (2013) and Rajagukguk (2016) argue that by building and improving future orientation, innovation and creativity, an entrepreneur is able to produce products according to market demands and will be able to read future business opportunities. The possibility of failure in business is an ever-present threat to entrepreneurs, there is no guarantee of success, challenges in the form of hard work, emotional pressure, and the risk of asking for a level of commitment and sacrifice (Purwanti, 2012). Nursiah et al (2015) stated that successful entrepreneurs are those who are able to survive, do not give up easily and are able to adapt to face difficult situations by making changes in their business. In other words, entrepreneurial behavior that has strong entrepreneurial characteristics has high motivation in running a business, not only wanting its business to run smoothly but wanting its business to develop and be sustainable. In addition, the research is in line with research conducted by Herminawati (2018) with the results of research that entrepreneurs who have strong entrepreneurial characteristics are human capital to achieve business sustainability.

➤ **H2: Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy partially has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability**

The test results on hypothesis 2 (H2) state that entrepreneurial self-efficacy partially has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. The findings of this study are in line with research conducted by Hamidah (2014), Mustofa (2014), Evaliana (2015), Widayoko (2016), Permatasari (2016), self-efficacy variables have a positive effect on entrepreneurial interest. Belief in one's own abilities is the basis for each individual to decide whether to take an action or not. The connection with business sustainability is that self-confidence makes an entrepreneur confident in his decisions and consistently makes his business sustainable. According to Laura (2010: 152) self-efficacy is a person's belief so that he can master a situation and produce various positive and useful results. Be positive and confident as a manifestation of the self-efficacy of an entrepreneur to be able to complete work effectively and efficiently so that his business will be sustainable. Self efficacy can be a determinant of the success of performance and work

implementation. Self efficacy also greatly affects the mindset, emotional reactions in making decisions.

Self-efficacy is a person's assessment of his own ability to carry out certain behaviors or achieve certain goals. Self efficacy can be a determinant of the success of performance and work implementation. Self efficacy also greatly affects the mindset, emotional reactions in making decisions. Someone who wants to be an entrepreneur must have high self-efficacy. Someone who wants to start entrepreneurship needs to have confidence in himself that he has good competence to do his own business. As an entrepreneur, it is very important to recognize his strengths and weaknesses (Sumarsono, 2010). Because entrepreneurs realize that the competence that is in them is the main capital to start their business and must have a high spirit to keep working to build the desired business.

➤ **H3: Karakteristik Entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability**

The test results on hypothesis 3 (H3) state that entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial self-efficacy simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. The findings of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Ana Tur Porcar et al, (2018), which states that the factors that are effective and affect entrepreneurship and business sustainability include entrepreneurial character and self-efficacy which are included in the scope of behavioral factors. The findings of this study are also in line with research conducted by Lighthelm. A.A (2010) that behavior in an entrepreneur is the main predictor for the sustainability of small businesses. The entrepreneurial behavior in question certainly includes entrepreneurial characteristics and self-efficacy.

In addition, this study is in line with the results of research conducted by Hernita et al, (2021) which showed that strengthening human resource capacity has a positive and significant correlation to the sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Strengthening the capacity of human resources certainly includes everything that is in entrepreneurs that can make a positive contribution to increasing productivity and sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to examine the effect of entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurial self-efficacy on business sustainability of fish catches of fishermen in Bonebolango Regency. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, entrepreneurial characteristics partially have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy partially has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability, and the characteristics of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial self-efficacy simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the sustainability of fishing business in Kabila Bone sub-district, Bonebolango district.

The limitation of this research is that the researcher can only explain the internal factors that exist in entrepreneurs while the external factors that affect business sustainability cannot be explained in this study. For further researchers, it is hoped that the results of this study can be used as a source of reference and further research on business sustainability.

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